

The case of equal co-authorship in scientific publications.

Steeds meer wetenschappelijke publicaties worden gevormd door gelijke contributies van meerdere auteurs. Dit artikel benadert dit fenomeen vanuit een normatief en conceptueel perspectief. Het biedt een filosofisch inzicht in een voorsnog nauwelijks geanalyseerd fenomeen en kan toekomstig onderzoek en initiatieven informeren.

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In its 2003 guide on authorship, the Committee On Publication Ethics (COPE) mentions *equal co-authorship* (hereafter called EC) as a legitimate possibility, as long as the roles of the equal authors are adequately disclosed: “Some groups list authors alphabetically, sometimes with a note to explain that all authors made equal contributions to the study and the publication. If you do so, make sure it is clear to the editor” (COPE 2003).

However, several commentators have voiced concerns about an increasing trend towards EC in scientific publications and a lack of clear guidance regarding them (Akhbarue and Lautenbach 2010, Wang et al. 2012, Li et al. 2013, Conte et al. 2013, Agoramoorthy 2016, Huang 2016, Lei et al. 2016).

This article will briefly discuss some normative and conceptual issues related to EC, clarifying what is at stake, and exploring its acceptability. EC directly reminds us that firstly, the practice of assigning authorship roles involves distributing something between co-authors. Secondly, it signals that something is being claimed by at least some equal authors that they could not otherwise claim, absent the possibility of EC.

This suggests that from an ethical point of view, one of the main issues raised by ECs is distributive justice, and from a conceptual perspective, EC seems to affect authors’ relationship with the work.

Distributive justice

Authorship credit is a way of allocating resources, and the underlying justice behind it raises both practical and normative questions regarding authors and their contributions to the published work. Of course social context is important here: authorship roles matter greatly to an academic’s career success (Biagoli 2003). In a very real sense, authorship is the academic coin of the realm.

From a regulatory perspective, COPE guidelines accept EC in a rather restricted manner, as they

require equal contributions of ‘ALL’ authors. This leaves a question mark when a combination of equal and unequal authors exist on the same manuscript (e.g. Zhang et al. 2007; Gerken et al. 2007).

From a normative perspective, since authorship credit entails no overtly tangible result, EC confronts us with an abstract form of distributive justice. That said, given the importance of authorship credit for success in academia, addressing the equality of success and its shortcomings sheds light on normative concerns about EC.

Ronald Dworkin’s definition of fair distribution of resources therefore will be useful here. His notion provides normative reasons for endorsing the *unequal* authorship model. He notes that an unequal distribution of resources is **fair** if “it results from the decisions and intentional actions of those concerned”.

Given that in the more commonly accepted norm of having only one first author, authorship sequence must be strictly agreed to by all coauthors (in case of disagreement, they can contact the editorial office), the non-EC system facilitates an unequal but **fair** distribution of resources (credit) according to Dworkin’s view.

Whether or not EC also produces a fair distribution of resources can be challenged. On EC, one or more persons are being made lead author, as compared to the total credit due to authors using more traditional unequal authorship designations. Consequently, EC can be viewed as unfair in two ways.

First, the use of EC by some is arguably unfair to authors who do not declare themselves to be equal co-authors even though they might meet EC’s vague criteria for this status. Effectively, their lack of the EC role may be taken to imply a lesser contribution to the work than they actually made, since they could have made themselves equal co-authors but did not. In practice, avoiding this perception may lead

to further increases in the use of EC. After all, all contributors might reason that granting equal lead co-authorship costs nothing to the individual who would otherwise be the sole lead author. He or she remains lead author.

Secondly, EC threatens a kind of unfairness to the broader scientific community. Accurately assessing individuals’ past contributions is crucially important to scientific progress, since that progress depends on allocating scientific jobs and opportunities to the most promising researchers available. Since EC threatens to obfuscate who has contributed ‘how much’, at least in small ways, it threatens to interfere with these allocations.

Insofar as it may possibly incentivize an over-claiming of credit, it may thus be inimical to the scientific reward system. It also may affect who takes accountability for the work, which can be an important issue if questions are raised regarding its integrity. EC may also cause practical problems: routine decisions that need to be made between journal editors and lead authors become potentially more complicated if more than one lead author is involved.

EC can be ethically problematic in another way as well. Regardless of whether or not EC becomes generally accepted, it will likely remain common practice in many contexts for papers to be cited by one lead author alone, e.g., Hosseini et al., 2017. However, when this shorthand reference convention is used, other lead authors fail to be mentioned at all.

If only one author is cited, the decision as to which author this is, will be arbitrary in one way or another. Whether it is determined by order of appearance on the byline, alphabetization, or some other criteria. Thus, even claiming co-equal lead authorship status for oneself on the manuscript may not ensure getting the full recognition one’s contribution deserves, in terms of one’s reputation in the broader community.

the accepted meaning of author by refusing to acknowledge the supremacy of one individual over others, and rearranges the way we think about scientific authorships.

One can argue that within the scientific authorship context where acts of authorship are placed in the bipolar field of true or false claims and conclusions, the form of author's relationship with the work is irrelevant, as long as they followed regulatory prescriptions (e.g. made a substantial contribution, did not plagiarize, etc.). That conclusion seems to follow Foucault's prediction that "It does not seem necessary that the author function remain constant in form, complexity, and even in existence" (Foucault 1979).

He added to his speculation that as a result of further development of the author function, the form of questions we ask about authorship and regarding 'who really spoke', will change. He predicted that those questions would change to "What are the modes of existence of this discourse? Where has it been used, how can it circulate, and who can appropriate it for himself? What are the places in it where there is room for possible subjects? Who can assume these various subject functions?" (Foucault 1979).

To be fair, we might already have some responses for those questions in the current context. Transposing his questions into our current scientific authorship practices yields interesting results:

What are the modes of existence of this discourse? (When was this article published and where were the experiments conducted?)

Where has it been used, how can it circulate, and who can appropriate it for himself? (In which journal was it published? Is the journal open access?)

What are the places in it where there is room for possible subjects? (Which resources and previous theories were used?)

Who can assume these various subject functions? (What were the peer-reviewers'/other scientists comments and reflections? How do the authorship roles relate to other institutional roles and structures, such as the mentor/trainee relationship, or the relationship between academia and industry?)

Discussion and conclusion

Although equality and attempts in establishing it in different contexts have been a major political and philosophical concern, EC seems unfair and opportunistic to observers who have voiced their concerns. This article focused on normative and conceptual aspects of EC, and its consequences for the relationship between author(s) and work.

In terms of justice and what EC means to the scientific community, using Dworkin's notion of fair distribution of resources, this article showed that since authors' consent to the conditions of equality is geared towards their own success, EC can be unfair to other scientists. Clearly, EC is a product of paying too much attention to bibliometric measures and productivity of scientists. It is a wonderful demonstration of what scientists' creativity looks like and as shown in this paper, follows what Foucault had predicted, namely that authorship is an evolving function that differs per period and discourse.

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